

SMART 01

Mobile technology

An introduction to mobile technology that can help to support active and healthy lifestyles to facilitate independent living. It covers some of the things to consider about buying and setting up mobile devices.

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of Technology

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SMART

MODULE 1

Mobile technology

Welcome to the SMART learning materials. This is the first of 8 SMART modules which covers some of the things to consider about buying and setting up mobile devices.

Introducing mobile devices

How confident are you with new technologies?

Would you like to become a more confident user of mobile devices and smart home technology?

The SMART learning modules are intended to provide a broad overview of how these exciting technologies can help to support active and healthy lifestyles to facilitate independent living.

This module is provided as an introduction to mobile technology.

What will you learn in this module

- 1 About different types of mobile devices.
- 2 Things to consider when choosing a mobile device.
- 3 Features of mobile devices and how to set them up.

Chapters in this module

1

Introduction to mobile devices

2

Choosing a mobile device that suits you

3

Device features and set up

4

Using your mobile device

SMART

MODULE 1

CHAPTER 1

Introduction to mobile devices

What can a mobile device do for you? As we will see, mobile devices have gone far beyond the original purpose of a phone that you could carry in your pocket. This chapter considers some of the benefits of using a mobile device.

What will you learn in this chapter

- 1 Some of the things you can do with a mobile device.
- 2 Different types of mobile devices and the evolution of mobile technology.
- 3 How mobile devices use has changed from phone calls to data.
- 4 Different types of phone contracts.

What can a mobile device do for you?

What is all this fuss about mobile devices? Why have they become so popular? Actually, it is mainly because they are really useful in so many ways.

Here are some of the ways that a mobile device could change how you do things.

How mobile devices can make a difference

1**2****3**

Staying in touch

Probably the main use of mobile technology is to stay connected to family and friends.

Mobile technology allows you to stay in touch even when you are physically far apart.

1

2

3

Meeting online

Mobile communication takes many forms. You can communicate via a voice or video call, or using text or multimedia-based communication. Mobile technology helps to bring families and friends together.

Those who don't use a phone miss this opportunity.

How mobile devices can make a difference

1

2

3

Avoid carrying a phone book in your purse/pocket

Phone books are large and heavy. With a smart phone, contact lists are a core feature.

A contacts list is like a phone book, you can use it to easily find the number of an old friend on your phone.

How mobile devices can make a difference

1

2

3

Getting to your destination

Journeys can be easier with mobile technology. You can book trains and flights without leaving your home or while you are on the go. You can check when the next train or bus is due so you are not waiting or you don't miss that connection!

How mobile devices can make a difference

4

5

6

Entertainment and interactivity

The mobile world is full of entertainment possibilities. Whether it is free entertainment such as online radio programmes, or short videos (YouTube), or subscription services for music, films, sport events - mobile devices can do that.

How mobile devices can make a difference

4

5

6

Don't miss your medication

Have you ever missed a medication dose? It's easy to forget unless you are very organised.

Mobile technology can help you to set up automatic reminders to remember to take your medication.

Lifestyle reminders

The HEALTHY modules talk about the importance of exercise for a healthy and balanced lifestyle.

Mobile technology can support exercise through the use of reminders, exercise apps (programmes that work on mobile devices) and smart watches.

Using your mobile device, you can also get reminders to drink your daily dose of water or fruit. Reminders are covered in SMART module 5.

SMART

4

5

6

Did you know?

Patients with a long-term illness often purchase medical devices that can be linked up wirelessly to their mobile device – so personal health information can be shared with their doctor.

A connected mobile device often called a ‘wearable’ can be an essential link between you and your physician. Wearables are covered in SMART module 6.

SMART

How mobile devices can make a difference

4

5

6

Sharing pictures videos and recordings

It is always nice to see photos of friends and family. With mobile technology you can share pictures and photos over long distances. It means that a family or group of friends can connect in this way even if they are in different countries.

Meet Maria, 84

Maria likes supporting her children, June and Jon.

She likes knitting, watching soap operas on TV, feeding pigeons dry breadcrumbs in the park.

Maria lives in a flat on the 3rd floor with no central heating and no lift.

Her pension is small, and her family is having serious financial difficulties.

She doesn't like technology and is anxious about using mobile devices.

Do the task!

Maria is not keen on technology; can you explain to Maria how mobile devices can help her?

- ✓ Meet and get to know Maria. [You can find information about Maria here.](#)
- ✓ Read back over the previous slides and from Maria's story think about how a mobile device can help her.
- ✓ What would you say to Maria about how a mobile device can help her?

Be a mobile foodie

With people spending more time at home, one common use for phones during the pandemic has been to share recipes and food ideas and to make shared cookbooks.

You can easily share pictures of your favourite healthy foods with your friends. You can also share a view from a hilltop or a funny scene.

What came before modern “smart” mobile devices?

1880s - first landline phone

As you may know, the phone was invented by Alexander Graham Bell in the 19th century.

Early 20th century phones

The phone didn't change much over the next 100 years. Here is how a phone looked in the early 1990s. Not much change from the 19th century!

1990s - mobile phones

The first mobile phone call was made in 1973. By the 1990s mobile phones were very popular. The first text message was sent in 1992. 1990s phones like the one in this picture fit in your pocket.

1990s - folding phones

Another small phone that was popular was the folding phone. This phone could basically just make calls and manage texts. Folding phones are still used and have become really small.

Phone drawers

Smartphones have evolved rapidly in recent years.

Many homes have a drawer full of old mobile phones. Modern phones contain rare expensive and reusable materials.

You should consider bringing your old phones to a recycling centre.

Mobile network history 2G to 5G and beyond

The phone networks that we use are being continuously upgraded to make them faster and add more features.

Modern phone systems use the 5G (5th generation) network, but before that there was 2G, 3G and 4G.

Each new network generation brings new features - from text to multimedia text, to full internet, to high speed internet that allows you to view videos from the internet.

Tablets are bigger...

Another mobile device that has become popular is the mobile tablet - which has a larger screen than a mobile phone, as can be seen in this image.

Some tablets are connected to the mobile phone 4G or 5G network, but many can only connect using a different wireless technology called Wi-Fi.

The rise of data...

Early mobile networks were designed for making calls. Today, phone networks support a variety of communication types. Modern phones communicate using “data” whether it is a phone call, an e-mail or a multimedia message. The phone technology considers each of these things to be just data to be transmitted.

Phone contracts

If you decide to buy a smartphone, you will need to think about how you will pay for access to the phone network to make your calls. This may be an issue for Maria because of her low income.

With landline phones, you typically paid per call. With modern phone contracts there is a lot more variety. This is good as it allows you to find the contract that suits you best.

Three types of phone network contracts

There are a few types of phone network contract. When choosing, it is important to ask if there is a minimum time on the contract. Sometimes this is one year. Here are three popular types of contract that you might wish to consider.

Pay as you go (PAYG)

No monthly fee and allows you to top up with credit when you need it. Phones and the cost of calls are generally more expensive as part of a PAYG package.

Monthly bill

You have to pay a fixed monthly amount and that includes a certain number of free calls and data. Phones are cheaper in these packages and also the cost of calls is lower.

SIM only

This type of contract is only for the SIM card, the little white card that goes into a phone. No phone is supplied, this assumes that you have one already. You are not paying for a phone, but calls can then be expensive.

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 SMART **MODULE 1** **CHAPTER 1** Introduction to mobile devices

Mobile phones are only for making phone calls

True

False

Chapter summary

1

Different ways to use a mobile device.

2

How the role of mobile devices have progressed from calls to handheld mini computer.

3

How the design of mobile devices has evolved.

4

Different types of phone contracts.

5

You have learnt some of the history of mobile technology.

6

You have learnt how modern mobile devices can be used.

7

The later chapters will address the topics of choosing and setting up a mobile device.

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

Knowledge of some of the uses of a mobile device.

2

Knowledge of how mobile devices have changed over time.

3

Awareness about phone contracts.

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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SMART

MODULE 1

CHAPTER 2

Choosing a mobile device that suits you

The previous chapter has outlined some important uses of mobile devices. This chapter will allow you to consider which type of mobile device suits you best by going through some of the main choices that are available to you.

Selecting a mobile device: the choice is yours

The process of selecting a mobile device involves a number of choices based on your preferences and characteristics and the technology readiness of your home and locality.

This chapter will briefly mention some of the things that you should consider when choosing a device.

What will you learn in this chapter

- 1 Some of the differences between smart phones and tablets.
- 2 Age-friendly devices that are easier to use and “smart” devices that have more features, but you may find more difficult to use.
- 3 Choices relating to network connection, phone features, and contracts.

Choose device type: phone or tablet?

First of all, you must ask yourself - do you want a tablet or a phone?

If you wish to use the mobile device when you are out of the home, then a phone is better as it allows you to make calls even when you are not near Wi-Fi.

Most tablets will only allow you to make social media calls in places where you can connect to Wi-Fi, such as at home or in a public space that offers free Wi-Fi. This will be covered in module SMART 2.

SMART

Software Choices: Android or iOS?

The picture shows a range of different screens on tablets and phones. The selection may seem intimidating, but really there are two main types of phone based on the software that controls them, Android and iOS.

Android based phones are cheaper generally and are more popular in many European countries.

iOS is used on Apple devices, and is good for accessibility. Both Android and iOS can be configured to use larger and more readable text by changing the accessibility settings.

Big or small?

Do you have problems reading on a small screen?

If the answer is yes, then you may prefer a mobile device with a large screen (e.g. a tablet).

On the other hand, do you prefer a phone that is small enough to fit in your purse or pocket? both Android and iOS devices allow you to make the screen text larger.

Choice on features: Full-featured or accessible mobile device?

If you select a modern mobile device, should it be a full featured smartphone/tablet or an accessible phone? Here are three options for you to consider.

Full-featured tablet or phone

There are two main choices for full featured mobile devices - tablet or phone? and iOS or Android?

Acorn accessible tablet

The Acorn tablet is specially designed to make it really easy to use.

Emporia accessible smartphone

The Emporia range of accessible smartphones are also designed to be really easy to use.

Choice of phone: Smartphone or button phone?

If you have decided on a phone, this next choice may be a difficult one. In chapter 1 you have learnt about some of the great benefits of using a smartphone. Be aware that it will take some time to learn how to fully use a smartphone.

We are guessing, you wouldn't be taking the time on this course if you didn't believe in the power of mobile devices for active and healthy ageing right? Please stay with us and see how you get on with a full-featured mobile device.

Choice of contract

For a mobile device that will use a mobile network connection, which type of contract will you pick, Pay As You Go, monthly bill or SIM only?

You should also consider how long the contract will be. How long will you need to pay before you can stop if you change your mind? This is an important question for the device seller to answer.

Wi-Fi and hotspots

Wi-Fi is a wireless technology that is available on most mobile devices. It can connect your mobile device to the internet in some places.

Wi-Fi hotspots that allow you to connect to the internet can be found in places like cafes and hotels and if you have an internet connection at home, it normally also includes Wi-Fi.

Is Wi-Fi available?

If you select a tablet without 4G connection, how will you get connected? Do you have access to Wi-Fi where you will use the tablet?

If you wish to use the tablet at home, do you have a network connection at home? If so, tablets usually come with Wi-Fi compatibility.

Camera choices

Do you like to take photos? If so, you might wish to select a mobile device that has a very good camera. The quality of the image on your device can be figured out by looking at the number of mega pixels for the camera on the feature list for the device in its documentation. Generally speaking, the more mega pixels the better.

The quality of the image is also determined by the optics. You can check if the optics of the phone camera is from a well-known camera company.

What to bring when buying a new mobile device

Now that you have decided on the mobile device that you like, it could be time to make the purchase. If you are going to buy a device with a contract-based mobile network connection, you may be required to bring the following documentation with you when signing the contract. These requirements will vary depending on the country, so you should check beforehand.

A form of identification

This could be a passport, driver's license or identity card.

A utility bill

An electricity bill, water bill or similar, to prove that you live at your address.

Bank account details

Details of the account that payments will be made out of if it is a monthly payment.

Do the task!

You have heard a lot about the choices for choosing a mobile device – which choices would you make?

- ✓ Which **software** should be on the phone? Android or Apple iOS?
- ✓ Do you prefer to have **large** text and icons and other accessible features?
- ✓ Is it important to have a **mobile network connection** or is Wi-Fi wireless connection sufficient?
- ✓ Do you travel between countries or prefer to have work and leisure connections on the same device? If so, do you prefer a device with **two SIM cards**?
- ✓ Is the **size** of the device important for you? Is the tablet a better option than a phone? Would you prefer a small and simple folding phone for example?
- ✓ Is it important for you to have a **good camera** on your device?
- ✓ Do you prefer a **full featured device?** (adaptable to your needs but complex) or simplified limited version?

Buying and downloading apps

Now that you have your mobile device you may wish to install programmes, called apps, to add to the pre-installed apps that are already on the device. You might use these apps to link your mobile device to a smartwatch or to hear the football results or for social networking.

To use an app, you often need to purchase it using your mobile device. Bear in mind that many apps put your data in the so-called "cloud". This is a security issue which will be covered in the SMART 4 module.

SMART

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 SMART **MODULE 1** **CHAPTER 2** Choosing a mobile device that suits you

Which of the following things are important to think about when choosing a mobile device?

- Should it be full-featured or accessible-with-restricted-features?
- The type of contract you will select
- Size of the device
- The colour
- Android or iOS?

Chapter summary

1

Smartphones and tablets: size and features.

2

Easy to use mobile devices versus more complex smart phones.

3

Other features of mobile devices that may affect your choice when buying.

4

This chapter has helped you to think about which device is best for your needs.

5

You should consider which device is likely to be fully used by you.

6

It is important that the choice of device does not limit your use or exclude you.

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

Recognising differences between smartphones and tablets.

2

Understanding of ease of use versus more powerful but challenging devices.

3

Appreciation of features of mobile devices that affect your choice.

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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Settings

SMART

MODULE 1

CHAPTER 3

Device features and set up

Once you have purchased a mobile device, the next step is to set it up. This chapter runs through some of the main steps in setting up your device from unboxing it to getting it connected and downloading apps.

What will you learn in this chapter

1 Starting your mobile device for the first time.

2 Some of the basic features of a mobile device.

What's in the box?

Have you found the right mobile device for you?

If so, congratulations on taking this important step!

Let's look first at what comes in the box.

What's in the box?

The device is generally packaged with a power cable, (sometimes) a charger and a small instruction leaflet.

Inserting the SIM card

If your device uses the mobile network, you will need to insert the SIM card that you have received with the device. To do this, you can use a specialised pin to open the little compartment for the SIM card which is located in the side of the device.

A small paper clip or an earring can also be used to open the SIM compartment.

Charge your device before use

Before you can check out the features of the mobile device, you must charge it, by connecting one end of the power lead into the phone and the other end into an electrical wall socket.

If you always fully charge your device to 100% charge, it will make the device last longer. Most devices make a recognisable beep when they begin and finish charging.

Different charging technologies for mobile devices

USB-C

Used on recent Android and iOS devices. Probably the most popular charging approach and may be used by all mobile devices by 2024. Can be plugged in two ways.

Micro USB

This is a slightly older connector that is used by Android devices and can only be plugged in one way.

Lightning USB cable

This type of connector was until recently used on all Apple devices such as the iPad and iPhone. Can be plugged in two ways.

Wireless charging

Wireless chargers like the one in this image don't need a cable to be connected to the device, but they don't charge as quickly or as well as wired chargers.

Save device power

There is a battery indicator on the screen of your device that tells you how much power is left. You can save power on your mobile device by selecting low power mode in the settings. You can also save power by limiting use of maps, social media and multimedia apps.

How devices break

It is difficult to break a mobile device while you are actually using it.

If a device won't start up, it is often because it is not properly charged. Sometimes the problem is the charging cable, which is cheap to replace.

Actually, most mobile device breakages happen when the device falls on a hard surface or into water.

Ways to protect a mobile device from breakages

You can protect yourself if your device breaks by taking out insurance on your device. This service is often offered by device sellers alongside the device contract and typically requires you to pay a monthly fee. Here are three ways to prevent breakages.

Protective covers

You can protect the device by buying a purpose built protective cover that can help if it falls.

Screen protector

A tempered glass screen protector helps to shield one of the most fragile parts of the device, the screen. This can be fitted in the phone shop.

Pop sockets

A pop socket connected to the back of the phone makes it easier to hold the phone. This reduces the risk of the device falling.

Do the task!

Maria is not confident about mobile technology. Can you help her get started with a phone?

- ✓ Meet and get to know Maria. [You can find information about Maria here.](#)
- ✓ Read back over the previous slides and think about the steps that she needs to go through to set up a mobile phone.
- ✓ What steps does Maria need to go through?

A review of features of a mobile device

Once your device is charged, let's take a tour of your device to see what it can do.

There are so many features on these rather small devices it is surprising that they can all fit in!

Let's begin our tour.

Features of a mobile device

1**2****3**

Power button

The thumb of this phone user is over the phone power button on the side of the phone. On some phones the power button is a small circular button on the front of the phone. By pressing and holding this button for two seconds you can turn off or turn on the phone.

1

2

3

Your power button

Have a look yourself at your own device and locate the power button.

It will be by itself somewhere around the edge of the mobile device. It may be on the top, bottom or side of the phone or tablet. If you are unsure, check in the instruction manual of your phone.

Features of a mobile device

1

2

3

Earpiece

Here is a phone user using earpiece mode. The ear piece is positioned near the top of the phone although it is difficult to see it. You can try to locate it by moving the phone around near your ear during a call to hear where the sound is coming from.

Features of a mobile device

1

2

3

The microphone (mic)

You can see that the phone user is now talking into the end of the phone. This is the part of the phone that picks up your voice as the microphone is located there.

A close-up photograph of a woman with dark skin and long braids. She is holding a black smartphone horizontally in front of her mouth. The phone is held between her fingers, with the top edge (where the microphone is) facing her. She has a slight smile and is looking towards the right. The background is a soft, out-of-focus light color.

1

2

3

Speaker mode

You will sometimes see phone users who have their phone in speaker mode, using the phone this way with the end of the phone and the microphone close to their mouth.

Using a phone in speaker mode, allows the other people in the room to hear what the caller is saying, but your mouth needs to be near the mic.

Features of a mobile device

4

Changing the earpiece or speaker volume

This phone user is about to tap a button on the side of the phone that adjusts the volume. There are two such buttons side by side - one for increasing and one for decreasing volume. Have a look yourself at your own device to find your volume buttons!

5

6

Features of a mobile device

4

5

6

Cameras

All modern phones and many tablets now have cameras. The quality of these cameras can vary. If you are keen on taking photos of things around you, consider buying a phone that is known to have a good camera.

4

5

6

Selfie cameras

Actually, modern phones and some tablets have a main camera on the back of the phone and a second camera on the front so you can make video calls and take "selfies".

Selfies are pictures that you take of yourself or a group of friends or family using your mobile device.

Cell towers

Look out in your neighbourhood for metal towers like the ones shown here. These are cell towers. They contain the antennas that mobile phones communicate with so that you can make calls and connect to the internet. They may be disguised as trees!

Phone reception is best at 50m from a cell tower but with clear line of sight, a cell tower can have a range of over 20km. You can search on the internet for the location of your nearest cell tower.

Features of a mobile device

4

5

6

Mobile network connections

To make a call or connect to the internet without Wi-Fi, your phone or tablet should be on and have a working SIM card with enough credit to make a call. The connection is automatic if your device is near a cell tower. In remote locations this won't work.

Features of a mobile device

7

8

9

Wi-Fi

Another way that your phone can connect for calls and texts, is using Wi-Fi. In this case the phone or tablet can link a Wi-Fi hotspot that is less than 10 or 15 meters away.

Mobile network versus Wi-Fi

So you can use Wi-Fi or a mobile network to make calls and send messages. What is the difference between the two approaches? Why do phones generally have both?

Mobile network connection

It operates over a long range, but you have to pay for the connection. You can generally make a call or send messages sometimes even in remote locations.

It's your choice

Wi-Fi connection

Wi-Fi operates only in a short range, but can be free. You may need to find a password to connect. It is usually fast but depends on the “contention” - the number of users connected to the same Wi-Fi.

The background features a complex digital landscape with various financial charts, including candlestick and line graphs, overlaid on a dark blue and black background. A bright light source in the top right corner creates a lens flare effect. In the foreground, a smartphone is shown with a person's silhouette on its screen. A vertical sequence of three boxes containing the numbers 7, 8, and 9 is positioned on the left side of the image. A network of colorful icons representing different digital services is located in the bottom left corner.

7

8

9

Mobile data allowance

Most mobile contracts include a **data allowance** - measured in Gigabytes (GB) - of how much mobile data you can use before you pay extra. 1 GB is a low monthly data allowance. Heavy use of social networks or video will use more than this. To save data, change your settings so apps using a lot of data only work with Wi-Fi, or turn off your data.

Features of a mobile device

Security by password

To help with the security of your device there are a number of passwords e.g. to unlock the phone features, for access to the Wi-Fi, for access to the SIM card.

Features of a mobile device

Security by thumb print, retina or finger gesture

Depending on the device type, you can also unlock your mobile device using a thumb print, pointing your phone camera at your eye's retina, or by sliding a pattern with your finger on the screen of the device. This is further explained in SMART 4.

SMART

A man in a brown shirt is shown in profile, holding a white smartphone up to a wooden door. He is using the phone to unlock the door. On the left side of the image, there is a vertical sequence of three numbered boxes: 7, 8, and 9. Box 9 is highlighted in black, while boxes 7 and 8 are white with black numbers. Arrows point downwards from box 7 to 8, and from 8 to 9.

7

8

9

NFC for locks

Some phones have a **near field communications** (NFC) feature, which allows them to interact with other electronic devices over short distances.

So for instance, this picture shows how NFC on a phone can unlock an NFC enabled door. Older phones do not have this feature, but it is becoming increasingly common.

A hand holding a smartphone over a payment terminal. The terminal is black with a keypad and a screen. A hand is pointing at the terminal. The background is a white counter with some papers and a blurred object.

7

8

9

NFC for payments

There is another handy use for NFC.

Using NFC on your phone, you can leave your bank card behind and use your phone to pay.

The NFC feature on the phone allows your phone to behave like a bank card. You need to be careful about security! Security of mobile devices is covered in SMART module 4.

SMART

Do the task!

What mobile device features would you show Maria?

- ✓ Meet and get to know Maria. [You can find information about Maria here.](#)
- ✓ Read back over the previous slides and from Maria's story. Think about what you can show her.
- ✓ Use a phone and work with another person. Pretend that you are showing the important features to Maria.

Do the task!

Which advanced feature of a mobile device would you find most useful or interesting? Would you recommend any to Maria?

- ✓ Using Near field communication feature on the mobile device to make payments or to open smart locks.
- ✓ A good quality camera on the device which can be used to take pictures or videos without fuss.
- ✓ The advanced authentication features such as face recognition, and thumb print recognition.
- ✓ Speaker mode or headphones which can help you to make calls or listen to music.
- ✓ Location awareness that allows you to find out where you are.

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 SMART **MODULE 1** **CHAPTER 3** Device features and set up

Which of these mechanisms can save power on your mobile device?

- Switching off the device when you are not using it.
- Minimising use of maps and social media
- Switching on low power mode
- Not using the device in locations with a good phone network signal

Chapter summary

1 Taking the mobile device out of the box.

2 Setting up your device for the first time.

3 Using the microphone and speakers.

4 Using the camera.

5 You have learnt how to get started with a new mobile device.

6 You have also learnt about some of the main ways of using the mobile device.

7 The following SMART modules will describe how to message or make calls.

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

- 1** Setting up a new mobile device.

- 2** Using the microphones and speakers.

- 3** Using the camera.

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

[Restart](#)[Next](#)

Module summary

1

This module has given an introduction to mobile devices.

2

You have learnt about different ways to use a mobile device and different mobile contracts.

3

How mobile devices moved from being only for calls to being mini- handheld computers.

4

You have learnt about the changes in the design of mobile devices.

5

You know about key features to consider when choosing or using a mobile device.

6

The main points of this module will be useful for progressing to later SMART modules.

Module completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this module!

Summary of acquired skills

1

You learnt what mobile devices are for, and some of their main features.

2

You learnt how to select a mobile device that suits your needs.

3

You learnt how to set up and start using a mobile device.

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this module or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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